

Argentina from new developmentalism to anarco-capitalism. What went wrong?

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Abstract

In the early 2000s, Argentina's national government embraced a new developmentalist strategy to recover from years of neoliberal rule. After the global crisis of 2008 and as China's irruption in the global economy consolidated, Argentina's economy, trapped in a peculiar form of Middle Income Trap, began a process of unstable and feeble growth, growing inflation, expanding fiscal and external disequilibria, and deteriorating labour markets and income distribution. New developmentalist hegemony (through different strategies and governments) could not sort out these issues in over 10 years, and its failures led to a radical turn in political events in late 2023. A new anarco-capitalist government was elected to erase all the new developmentalist heritage.

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Introduction

In the last five years, there has been significant discussion in Latin America regarding the crisis of the new developmentalist project that emerged from the remnants of neoliberalism in the late 1990s (Féliz, 2025). Paradoxically, this occurs as a new wave of developmentalism, state capitalism, or developmental state is gaining momentum in the global north (e.g., Alami, 2023; Mazzucato and Monaco, 2024; Singh, 2022).

In the English-speaking world, the seminal book by Bresser-Pereira, Oreiro and Marconi (2015) a reference in the new developmentalist debate in core countries. However, the discussion in Latin America in Portuguese and Spanish, especially in Brazil and Argentina, sparked at least a decade earlier (Bresser-Pereira, 2010; Bresser-Pereira and Oreiro, 2010; Féliz, 2006, 2007, 2008).

In Argentina, new developmentalism became the dominant ideology for the political coalitions formed in response to the neoliberal crisis (Féliz, 2006). Both progressive and conservative political forces, along with the major sectors of capital and labor, found in a renewed centrality of the state a means to articulate development strategies beyond the market.

However, in less than a decade, new developmentalism reached its limits, and in Argentina, it underwent a transitional crisis that, through a turbulent process, led to a radical socio-political shift towards Javier Milei's anarcho-capitalist far-right. Research on the consolidation and crisis of new developmentalism, and its connections with the rise of the ultra-right in Argentina, is just beginning.

From the field of Latin American Marxist political economy, particularly from dependentism, there are several studies that emphasize the difficulties of new developmentalism in overcoming the structural constraints of dependent capitalism. There has not yet been sufficient reflection on the political economy of these difficulties. This article aims to contribute elements to the critical analysis of new developmentalism and its trajectory, as well as its role in the rise of anarcho-capitalism in Argentina.

Beyond this introduction, in the next section we present the main traits of the new developmentalist debate. In section 2 we analyze the birth, consolidation and crisis of new developmentalism in Argentina, accounting for the main drivers of the process. In section 3, we describe how the crisis of new developmentalism in Argentina creates the pre-conditions for the rise of the anarcho-capitalist experiment. In section 4, we briefly present the main traits of the economic strategy of this new political coalition. Finally, we present some relevant conclusions.

The bare bones of new developmentalism. A brief characterization

In the aftermath of the debt crisis and the end of neoliberal dominance in the 1990s, the 21st century sparked a debate in Latin America on how to reorient development strategies. In this context, and amid a wave of intense social struggles, a new economic policy consensus began to emerge: new developmentalism. This strategy drew on the principles of the old developmentalism in the style of ECLAC, while also offering a profound critique of the advance of neoliberal doctrines and the structural adjustments promoted by international lending agencies (Féliz, 2025).

The new hegemonic neo-developmental consensus had regional variations but was based on several common points. It generally accepted the structural characterizations of ECLAC's structuralist developmentalism, including the tendency towards falling terms of trade, the thesis of underdevelopment in the peripheries as a counterpart to development in the center, and the need to protect industry (Bresser-Pereira and Gala, 2010: 6). New developmentalism incorporated a conceptual framework that emphasized the need to guarantee certain macroeconomic balances. Firstly, backward countries need to maintain a competitive (strong dollar) and stable real exchange rate (Bresser-Pereira and Gala, 2010: 8). Under these conditions, the economy could ensure the development of an industrial platform capable of facing global competition using state-of-the-art technology. Similarly, the stability of the high exchange rate would favor investment and foster long-term job creation (Frenkel, 2005; Frenkel and Rappetti, 2004).

Secondly, a high exchange rate, above the level that balances the current account of the balance of payments, would help offset other structural elements of peripheral economies, which are incorporated into the design of new developmentalist macroeconomic policy: the tendency for the exchange rate to appreciate and the 'Dutch disease' (Bresser-Pereira and Gala, 2010: 8-9; Bresser et al, 2015: 56-73). The argument is that the cyclical dynamics of the real exchange rate in peripheral countries tend to appreciate (lower the relative price of the dollar in local currency) due to the presence of highly competitive export sectors linked to the extraction of natural resources. Without exchange rate management, the exports of these sectors (usually ground-rent appropriators) put downward pressure on the real exchange rate, making local production more expensive and increasing the consumption of foreign currency for imports of goods (especially luxury consumer goods) and services (especially international tourism and freight). Although this dynamic deteriorates the balance of payments, in the short term, it can be compensated through the inflow of speculative capital, which, in turn, can accentuate the exchange rate appreciation.

Governments often leverage exchange rate appreciation to their advantage, promoting a form of 'exchange rate populism' (Bresser-Pereira and Gala, 2010, p. 9) and forms of 'fiscal populism' that garner support from the middle and upper-middle classes (Bresser-Pereira et al, 2015: 168-170), who can emulate the consumption patterns of central countries from peripheral structural bases. Eventually, international financing is abruptly cut off, leading to a sharp devaluation of the local currency and replicating the historical pattern of instability. This tendency towards macroeconomic instability, linked to a novel interpretation of the 'external constraint' (Diamand, 1972), results in speculative, rent-led investment patterns. These patterns are associated with a strategy of adapting to short-term opportunities in the external sector (Nochteff, 1995). Such 'soft' adaptation strategies favor the development of non-innovative and non-transitory monopolies, which perpetuate the general conditions of macroeconomic instability.

According to Bresser-Pereira, in the new developmentalism "a moderate interest rate and a competitive exchange rate are more important than industrial policy" (Bresser-Pereira, 2010: 123). Against the neoliberal rentier–financier class coalition's defense of high interest rates and low inflation (Bresser-Pereira et al), the new developmentalist consensus promotes responsible fiscal practices and moderate interest rates: "This is the political tripod of the new developmentalism" (Bresser-Pereira, 2010: 129). It proposes control over the state's public accounts to ensure a positive level of public savings (primary fiscal surplus) and low state debt, together with control over the nation's current account balance of payments.

Finally, in a strategic shift, new structuralism emphasizes the need to support export-led growth, at least in a transitional stage to a higher-development regime (Bresser-Pereira et al, 2015: 123-134). Bresser-Pereira highlights that "in the era of globalization, export-led growth is the only sensible strategy for developing countries" (Bresser-Pereira, 2010, p. 158), but he clarifies that this is only viable "as long as they have the competitive advantage of cheap labor" (Bresser-Pereira, 2010: 158). In this context, these authors advocate for an accumulation pattern that ensures unit labor costs are kept in check (Curia, 2007: 65), meaning that wage increases are aligned with rising labor productivity (Bresser-Pereira et al, 2015: 165-168). Curia refers to this policy as "wage-beaconing" (Curia, 2007: 120), which prioritizes "the formidable capital formation effort required for the sustainability of the model" (Curia, 2007: 99) and demands a balanced approach between accumulation and distribution through an active income policy. Wage-restraints are defended as they will foster higher rates of investments and are "purely temporary because, in the medium and long term, the higher economic growth made possible by the exchange rate devaluation and the ensuing increase of investment opportunities will enable a more pronounced pace of labour productivity growth ... thus

favouring a faster growth in real wages” (Bresser-Pereira et al, 2015: 168-169). A prominent figure in Argentine developmentalism noted that 'it is necessary to make the increase in the wage-earner's share of income compatible with the expansion of savings and accumulation' (Ferrer, 1980: 122). This underscores the need to manage wage demands to achieve a real exchange rate that supports sufficient internal savings to sustain capital accumulation (Bresser-Pereira, 2010, p. 160; Bresser-Pereira et al, 164-170). Wage-beaconing integrates “the process of capital formation and the distributive formula” (Curia, 2007: 120).

Argentina: From recovery and consolidation to hitting a wall and a long transitional crisis

In several South American countries, new developmentalism consolidated with its own characteristics as it emerged from the crisis of neoliberalism. In the case of Argentina, the neoliberal era reached its peak at the end of the 1990s. From 1998 onwards, the country was hit by a succession of crises in different regions of the global south (Brazil, Russia, Southeast Asia), the development of its contradictions, and the consolidation of anti-neoliberal mass movements. The structural adjustment program known as the Convertibility Plan began a path of disaster. By the end of 2001, the accumulated contradictions exploded, weakening the already fragile neoliberal hegemony (Bonnet, 2006; Dinerstein, 2002; Féliz, 2011), and paving the way for a new developmentalist order.

Starting point and recovery of the economy after de 2001 crisis

In the case of Argentina, the new development program took shape within a specific local and regional framework. The exit from convertibility resulted in the partial cessation of payments on the external public debt and the reduction of real wages (both in the private and public sectors) due to the violent devaluation of the national currency (the peso). This dual movement quickly led to a double surplus in the fiscal and external accounts. The real currency devaluation promoted the expansion of exports, especially primary exports, in a favorable global context. The emergence of China in global trade after it entered the WTO in 2000 led to a significant increase in the international prices of Argentina's main export commodities (i.e., Soya) (see Figure 1); terms of trade reached a peak in 2012 and then stagnated. Foreign trade became strongly surplus, and the Central Bank of Argentina (BCRA) was able to accumulate international reserves (see Figure 1). International reserves also peaked in 2012 and then fell sharply within a few years, subsequently recovering only thanks to new borrowing. Additionally, the impact of the fall in the wage bill also favored the expansion of the export balance.

Figure 1. International reserves and terms of trade

Source: INDEC, BCRA.

Note: International reserves (Red dotted line), Terms of Trade Index (blue full line).

In parallel, the fiscal surplus policy was bolstered by the fall in public sector wages, the partial default on public debt, and the introduction of a new tax on agricultural exports (export taxes, “retenciones”). This last measure had a dual purpose. Firstly, in 2004, the export tax accounted for almost 14% of the national public sector's total income, thereby strengthening the weakened public finances. Secondly, withholding taxes served as a mechanism to absorb a portion of the ground-rent reflected in the value of primary product exports. In this regard, the tax was seen as a way to mitigate the anti-industrial effect of a potential “Dutch disease” (Bresser-Pereira et al, 135-150). The tax not only allowed the state to appropriate part of the ground-rent but was also estimated to reduce the domestic price (in local currency) of export products. Consequently, the withholding taxes had another implicit objective: to curb the inflationary impact of the initial devaluation and contain food prices to limit the wage and income demands of the popular classes mobilized at the end of the Convertibility. Simultaneously, and with similar objectives, a policy of

subsidized prices for public services (i.e., electricity, gas, water, public transport) was established, with a growing fiscal cost (Bona, 2012), along with a broad but basic social policy based on income transfer programs (Pérez et al., 2006).

New development ‘in regime’

This macroeconomic framework fueled an accelerated expansionary dynamic in the initial stage and is now “in regime”. Until the 2008 global crisis, the Argentine economy grew by an average of 8.8 percent annually (2002-2007), inflation remained around 8.1 percent annually (2003-2007), and formal employment increased by 2.1 million jobs (2002-2008). As suggested by Bresser-Pereira and his co-authors (Bresser-Pereira et al, 2015), the objective of sustaining over-growth was supported by a combination of a high but declining real exchange rate, low real interest rates (between 2003 and 2012, the average monetary policy rate remained at 7.09 percent while inflation averaged 8.7 percent; Federico Glodowsky, 2022), and a policy of wage restraint. However, contrary to the new developmentalist expectations (Bresser-Pereira et al, 2015: 156-163) and despite the recovery of the profit rate compared to the 1998-2002 crisis (see Figure 2), the investment rate did not manage to overcome mediocre values: according to INDEC (National Institute of Statistics and Census) data, the rate of gross fixed investment did not exceed 19.8% of GDP between 2003 and 2007, averaging 17%. Figure 2 shows that after the crisis of 2001, capital formation remained around a historically low 20% of GDP. As warned by critics from dependency and classical structuralist traditions, low interest rates and appreciated exchange rates promoted an expansion in conspicuous consumption at the top of the income distribution.

Figure 2. Profit rate and gross fixed capital formation

Source: INDEC, BCRA.

Note: Profit rate (red dotted line) and Gross Investment in Fixed Capital (% of GDP; blue full line). Note 2: Profit rate is my own estimate based on the survey of 500 biggest firms of INDEC. Latest data reaches 2023.

In the process, the conditions that initially allowed the expansion to take place deteriorated. The government of Néstor Kirchner (2003-2007), followed by Cristina Fernández de Kirchner (2007-2011, 2011-2015), faced the need to simultaneously create conditions of macroeconomic and socio-political stability. In Argentina, the new development project was not born out of a plan or a manual, but out of this necessity (Féliz, 2016).

While the government sought to contain wages with a strategy of “beaconing” (Curia, 2007), pressure from trade union organizations grew. Although the majority of trade union organizations supported the process of economic expansion and provided political backing to the new government, they simultaneously strengthened their capacity to demand the recovery of wage losses from the period prior to 2003. This pressure was channeled institutionally through joint negotiations with companies and state mediation. Until 2012, the wage dispute led to a significant recovery in real wages among formalized and unionized workers in the private sector, mostly adult males; in the public sector, wage recovery was slower. Within a framework of flexible monetary policy (i.e., without the restrictions of the convertibility regime of the 1990s), the distributional struggle was partially channeled into inflationary pressures (Féliz, 2007; Piva, 2015), which began to impact the high dollar policy.

In parallel, the state sustains and expands income transfer policies, which are mostly directed—by design and the social and sexual division of labor—towards young and racialized women (Brown, 2020; Félix and Díaz Lozano, 2018). On the one hand, universal but basic social programs were consolidated, from the Unemployed Heads of Households program (which reached more than one million people in 2002) to the re-nationalisation in 2008 of the Retirement and Pension Fund Administrators (AFPJ) system, which had been privatized in 1993, and from there to the creation in 2009 of the Universal Child Allowance (Asignación Universal por Hijo/a). Taken together, these transfers represent benefits below the minimum wages received by formalized men. Alongside social transfers, a policy of subsidies to public service tariffs is being consolidated (Bona, 2012), which, unlike the mentioned cash transfers, has a more direct impact on the middle sectors with access to public services, which, despite the public works policy, continue to be limited. These policies consolidate a significant increase in national public spending and strain the fiscal surplus, given the state's limited political will to broaden the tax base.

While the economy expands within a favorable international framework, the national government capitalizes on the conditions created by the 2001 crisis, accumulating international reserves in the Central Bank and ensuring a policy of low real interest rates. However, this policy did not significantly encourage private investment, contrary to theoretical expectations (Bresser-Pereira, 2010). Large companies did not translate their higher profits into significantly higher rates of investment in constant capital, continuing to favor 'soft options' (Nochteff, 1995). After the global crisis of 2008, the collapse of the profit rate solidified this pattern.

In this context, the government sought to resolve the external debt crisis by promoting a process of renegotiation of the defaulted debt (F. J. Cantamutto, 2023). In 2005, it carried out a first debt swap for new securities, significantly reducing the amount owed to private investors, and in 2006, the accumulated debt with the International Monetary Fund (IMF) was paid in full. By 2010, the renegotiation with external private creditors was completed; however, a smaller percentage of creditors did not accept the agreements (vulture funds, holdouts), which led to a litigation process. This issue was only resolved in 2016 when a more conservative government (Mauricio Macri, 2015-2019) paid the full amount of the holdouts' claims, enabling a temporary process of external indebtedness. The paradox of the renegotiations at the heart of new developmentalism (2003-2015) is that they did not dispel doubts about Argentina's financial capacity, as the repayment of the renegotiated debt was made without roll-over. Until 2016, international capital refused to finance the process of capital accumulation in Argentina, favoring instead the change in the composition of public debt towards debt in national currency, but at the cost of

the deterioration of the Central Bank's international reserves (see Figure 1). In comparison, Brazil (Argentina's neighbouring giant and main trade partner) peaked its reserves in 2019, and kept a sizable stock there on.

The BCRA's reserves was used to pay the debt to international creditors in a context of growing exchange rate appreciation and a decline in the trade balance. Inflationary pressures and the classic 'exchange rate populism' that favors middle-class consumption, combined with a significant error in energy policy, have exacerbated the situation. In 2012, the national government decided to partially re-nationalize the main oil company (YPF), which had been privatized in the 1990s (F. J. Cantamutto, 2020). Until then, the privatized YPF had been depleting proven oil and gas reserves, leading the country to a growing energy deficit in foreign trade. With the recovery of YPF (with 51% of the shares in the hands of the national state), the development of new shale oil and gas deposits was promoted, to be explored and exploited together with Chevron using hydraulic fracturing techniques (fracking). Although this process would eventually help reverse the external deficit, until the early 2020s, the loss of foreign currency deepened a typical balance of payments crisis with clear inflationary consequences.

Global crisis, stagnation and war of attrition: nursing the anarco-capitalist monster in a dependent economy

The global crisis of 2008 transformed the contradictions and barriers of the new developmentalist program into limits. The second decade of the 21st century appears as a new lost decade (Féliz, 2013): the production of wealth stagnates and becomes unstable. Between 2011 and 2022, GDP per capita fell by 8.9%. In contrast, while Brazil slowed its growth rate, it did not stagnate.

The process of stagnation accelerates the contradictions of the new developmentalist program. In our view, these contradictions manifest both locally and globally. As we have pointed out, the government faced increasing difficulties in sustaining a high and stable real exchange rate, while the trade balance and fiscal results deteriorated and inflation accelerated. Additionally, the shock of the emergence of Chinese capitalism on the global scene was becoming more pronounced. As investment stagnated, industrial value addition declined, and imports of goods from China multiply (see Figure 3), Argentina as a country with medium levels of development, historically tied to a weak and variable connection with the region's sub-imperial power (Brazil), was confronting the very limits of its dependent economy. Argentina's industrial matrix now faces the risk of collapse. With ups and downs, profitability has been consistently falling since 2006 (see Figure 2).

Figure 3. Share of imports of goods from China to Argentina

Source: INDEC

This process leads to a loss of dynamism in formal employment (closely linked to industrial activity) and the multiplication of self-employment and entrepreneurship. Combined with wage stagnation, the conditions for a long cycle of deterioration in the material living conditions of the population begin to take shape.

A transitional crisis is beginning to emerge in new developmentalism. Within the dominant developmentalist strategy, this crisis implies a desperate search, albeit with trials and errors (Álvarez Huwiler and Bonnet, 2018), for a solution to the contradictions that feed these imbalances. Initially, this was our interpretation (Féliz, 2014). We understood that the dominant sectors and their political representation in the state sought to spatially and temporarily displace the contradictions of the new developmentalist regime of accumulation while looking for political solutions that would allow them to be productively channeled within it. During the 2000s, Argentina's dependent economy was able to sustain the myth of growth with inclusion, as the loss of value in the global market (unequal exchange "outwards") was compensated for by forms of super-exploitation of labor, nature, and women's bodies (unequal exchange "inwards") (Féliz, 2019). The exhaustion of the expansionary cycle of the global market from 2007/2008 onwards marked the limits of the strategy. From then on, the pressure to compensate for the conditions of dependency became unsustainable. This is expressed both in the tensions in the space of direct capital production/appropriation and in state mediation (i.e., public policy).

Between 2011 and 2015, during her second term, Cristina Fernández de Kirchner (CFK) sought to address the difficulties of accumulation through what she called 'fine tuning.' However, the effect of the austerity policy led to the fracture of the ruling coalition and its defeat in 2015 (Félic, 2016). The government of Mauricio Macri (2015-2019) accelerated and expanded these initiatives but ultimately also failed. While expanding access to external financing, both governments pushed for fiscal 'reordering' (particularly reducing economic subsidies) to limit the destabilizing pressures of rising fiscal and external deficits. The Macri government sought to advance the adjustment process without dismantling the general new developmentalist pattern, starting with the acceleration of macroeconomic adjustment within the framework of a new cycle of external indebtedness (F. J. Cantamutto and Schorr, 2016; Félic, 2017).

Neither CFK's fine-tuning nor Macrismo's phased adjustment managed to resolve macroeconomic contradictions. Instability and general stagnation deepened, inflation accelerated at ever higher rates, and the fiscal and external deficits consolidated. By 2018, the corrective process initiated in 2013 had broken down. The political blockage to attempts to relaunch accumulation led to an accelerated form of the crisis. The return of the IMF (International Monetary Fund) in 2018 marked a new stage. From that moment on, the transitional crisis seemed to change in nature, opening the space for a more radical change in the regime of accumulation. Much in the same way, in Brazil, during Dilma Rousseff's government (2011-2016), economic policy tilted towards austerity. While attempting to reduce the fiscal deficit, the PT's new developmentalist coalition fractured in 2016. This eventually led to a radical turn to the right with the election of Jair Bolsonaro as president.

In a war of attrition against workers' resistance to adjustment, the economic crisis and instability that the Argentine economy has been experiencing for more than ten years have operated as mechanisms for the disarticulation of popular resistance and favored general social implosion (Gago and Barttolotta, 2024). Extended social programs act as a buffer, making a 2001-style social explosion less likely. This is the context in which the hegemonic project (based on a new figuration of productive-reproductive labor and the super-exploitation of women's bodies) is blocked, as it cannot guarantee the long-term reproduction of its forms of legitimization. The 'political composition' (Pitts, 2024) of the working people underwent a new mutation during the decade, now within the socio-political space of the new developmentalist social formation. In this framework, the political forces that promote the new developmentalist articulation see the materiality of the political relations that place them in the leadership of the power bloc dissolve. Income redistribution sought to articulate a matrix of appropriation dominated by men in formal employment, while women were institutionalized as a reproductive labor force. However, as the

precarious redistributive matrix loses its material foundations, political forces in the state lose their capacity for hegemonic articulation. With secular stagnation, loss of income, and the crisis of a new developmentalist state in the process of austerity, the new developmentalist coalition is defeated by its own limits.

Milei's government: Is there anything left of the new developmentalist hegemony after the "chainsaw" and the "blender"?

The new developmentalist project encountered its own limitations due to the inability to overcome the restrictions inherent in the dependent condition of the Argentine economy and the disconnection of political representation in the face of the deterioration of the material conditions for the reproduction of life.

The election of Javier Milei at the end of 2023 signifies the structural crisis of the new developmentalist project. With a political program centered on the adjustment of the state and its political representation (the political "caste"), Milei triumphed in the second round of elections. Two decades of new developmentalist hegemony seem to be coming to an end. On the one hand, the strategy of maintaining a stable and expensive dollar to mitigate the impact of the 'Dutch disease' effect has failed. Without sustained access to the international capital market, exchange rate appreciation contributes to the deterioration of macroeconomic balances. When access to external borrowing was finally restored in late 2015, it accelerated imbalances, led to unsustainable over-indebtedness, and extended the crisis.

At the same time, the neo-development strategy is called into question by the economy's inability to create material conditions for the reproduction of life through formal employment in the private sector or in the state. The stagnation that began in the second decade of the 20th century favours a discourse against the state as an organiser. The idea of the 'present state', capable of solving the problems of everyday life, began to be tendentially replaced by a valuation of the 'state as an obstacle'. Fractions within the popular sectors, particularly the youth, are beginning to perceive limits to the state's capacity to solve their problems. In the dominant sectors, faced with the structural crisis posed by China's irruption, the discourse of reducing the state and its fiscal burden began to multiply. In both cases, the new developmentalist hypothesis of the state as the creator of the general conditions for capitalist social reproduction is losing ground. The social base of a broad right-wing coalition is gradually consolidating. At the end of 2019, during the last attempt of the traditional right to govern through the transitional crisis of new development, Macri loses the elections but receives more than 40% of the votes in the midst of a steely crisis. Four years later, Milei will build his electoral base from that starting point.

This context enables Milei's government to accelerate fiscal austerity and restructuring of the economy. Self-defined as anarcho-capitalist, the

government is accelerating the retrenchment of the state through a combination of ‘chainsaw’ and ‘blender’ policies. The former involves the elimination of thousands of jobs in the public sector in parallel with the elimination of programmes, institutions and ministries at the national level. The second refers to the brutal decline in real terms of state spending in key areas, such as pensions, public works, subsidies for public services, and science, technology, education, and health policies. In a few months, national public spending will be sharply reduced (25.9% in 2024). Simultaneously, through the Basic Law and a series of decrees of Necessity and Urgency, the government deregulates numerous sectors of the economy and activities, accelerating the process of regressive income redistribution against the popular classes. Finally, through a regime of incentives for large investments (RIGI), the government seeks to promote the expansion of strategic sectors, fundamentally in mining and hydrocarbons, to clear the balance of payments.

Although the macroeconomic underpinnings of the crisis do not yet seem to have been cleared up, nor the structural determinants resolved, two years after Milei's election, the new developmentalist discourse has lost much of its strength in the political space.

Conclusions

The new development strategy in Argentina was born out of the crisis of the neoliberal programme at the turn of the twentieth to the twenty-first century. This new programme was constructed as part of the need for the political system and new forces in government to create a certain political hegemony. New developmentalism as a strategy was consolidated with this need.

The new developmentalism that spread across parts of Latin America and influenced other regions of the global south sought to overcome the limits that blocked classical developmentalism. With critical reflection in the light of the decades of neoliberal hegemony, the new developmentalism proposed a strategy that could lead dependent and peripheral countries beyond their structural limitations. However, the proposal embodied in Argentina was only able to consolidate itself in an international context that was very favourable but which at the same time augured new challenges, especially after the global crisis of 2008.

Time did not work in favour of a programme of very moderate reforms in a context of global transition and systemic instability. Its golden age lasted less than a decade, and its crisis (which initially seemed transitional) has now extended for more than 10 years.

The new developmentalist programme in Argentina faced serious difficulties in avoiding the tensions that the conceptual framework itself

recognised. On the one hand, the tendencies towards exchange rate appreciation, due to structural (Dutch disease-type effects) and political (exchange rate populism) factors, converged with strategic errors (energy trade balance crisis) and structural restrictions (over-indebtedness in foreign currency) that could not be cleared. This tensions let to recurrent foreign exchange crisis, insufficient levels of capital capital accumulation, and instability.

On the other hand, social class-conflict was channelled into inflationary pressures and loose fiscal and monetary policies instead of undertaking a more sustainable distributive path. Given that the dominant sectors continued to favor soft investment options, without long-term commitments, rather than accepting a new “social pact” that was fairer to the working classes, the expected class compromise was not viable. Or, for it to be possible, it required workers to accept impossible conditions. The new developmentalist pact and its “distributive formula” (Curia, 2010: 120) was not tenable. Thus, in this context, and as the transitional crisis deepened, dominant fractions of capital increasingly favored a winner-takes-all position.

The result of this combination, that stalled economic growth, was a war of attrition against the resistance of the working classes. This destroyed the credibility of the state-centric new developmentalist strategy, fractured the new developmentalist coalition (Félic, 2016), and consolidated a social alliance in favour of radical political orientation towards the anarcho-capitalist ultra-right.

The anarcho-capitalist programme is presented as the last adjustment to end all adjustments. The prolonged transitional crisis within new developmentalism left an exhausted society, surrendered to the need for a different way out. Having discarded the alternative of a superior new developmentalist option (which could attempt to take the country closer to the more developed countries), the dominant sectors in Argentina opted for the anarcho-capitalist option, which promises to break the blockade to Argentina’s development by taking a downward path to bring the country closer to the neighbouring countries. Between the option of trying to be Germany, or even Ireland within a few decades (as president Milei proposed), and trying to be Peru (e.g., extractivist, highly unequal, politically unstable), the ruling bourgeoisie seems convinced that it can now impose the last option.

Whilst an alternative position and a new social subject for social change are still missing, a few things have become clear. First, without breaking productive and financial dependency, no developmentalist option seems realistic in Argentina (Félic, 2024). Dispensing with dependency is the key to any alternative development path (Marini, 2022). Second, macroeconomic balances cannot be built outside a successful coalition with the working classes at its core. Any attempt to “beacon” the needs of the masses within the needs of

capital, will have a hard time to create a lasting developmentalist coalition, especially in a pluralistic political system. Finally, macroeconomic equilibriums and export-led growth, do not replace the need for a more inclusive, participatory, and need-oriented development strategy, to overcome Argentina's dependent status.

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